

From Science Fiction to Science Fact: A Mars Warming Precursor Mission for the Next Decade

Introduction

Today, Mars is inhospitable to humans: it's too cold for liquid water given its thin 6 mbar atmosphere that lacks oxygen, and it exposes the human body to reduced gravity and significant radiation. While we cannot do much about the reduced gravity, we can tackle the other elements across a wide range of timelines, from a few years to centuries.

Fig. 1 The near-term, mid-term and long-term steps towards terraforming Mars [1]

Whether humanity should change the climate of Mars in order to make it more hospitable to humans is an open question. In order to be able to answer it in an informed manner we must understand what it would take to warm Mars, increase its O₂ levels and increase its atmospheric pressure [2]. Global scale Mars terraforming would be a long and costly process that would take at least centuries. In order to make the problem tenable, we need to break it up into smaller chunks and crucially develop a mission concept that can de-risk one of those chunks while not taking 100 years to implement and costing \$100 B+. Here we explore a realistic concept for a Mars surface payload that can answer critical questions about the first step in terraforming - warming the surface of Mars by 35 °C to have regions of Mars rich in surface or near-surface water ice that get diurnal average temperatures above 0 °C.

The Warming Method

The mission concept discussed is centered around a novel and potentially very effective method to warm Mars: through the release of engineered aerosols. Recent work by Ansari et al. [3] and Richardson et al. [4] shows that artificial aerosols made from materials that are readily available at Mars could warm the planet 5000 to 10000 times more effectively per unit mass than the most powerful greenhouse gases. The aerosols would be released from the surface, lofted into the atmosphere by Martian winds, and distributed globally in a matter of weeks. The warming effect would be fast on a planetary timescale, with a global average warming of the Martian surface of at least 35 K potentially achievable in just 3-4 years.

Fig. 2 The proposed engineered aerosol warming method [3]

The engineered aerosols are designed to strengthen the natural greenhouse effect of Mars by letting sunlight through to the surface (around 5-600 W/m² at Mars and 50-200 W/m² at the surface) while preventing IR radiation from escaping to space. The aerosols themselves could be made out of a number of materials including metals (ribbons, rods, rings, or disks 8-9 micron in longest dimension, or aggregates) and graphene (disks of various sizes in the nano scale). Figure 3 shows several aerosol options, both for warming Mars and for precursor mission testing (see the silica nanospheres).

Fig. 3 (a) Aluminium nanorods 9 µm x 160 nm [3]; (b) Aluminium nanoribbons [Mohseni group, Northwestern University]; (c) Graphene disks [5]; (d) Magnesium aggregate [Boies group, Stanford University]; (e) Silica nanospheres [6]; (f) Al oxide nanospheres [7]

More details on the warming method are available in [3-4], [8].

Why a Mars Aerosol Release Test?

The Ansari et al. study [3] assumes that the engineered aerosol can be lofted by the Martian winds above the Planetary Boundary Layer (PBL, the region of the atmosphere most

affected by the surface), which extends up to 5 km in altitude on Mars compared to 1-3 km on Earth, to then achieve global dispersal. However, the properties of the Martian PBL are difficult to study from orbit, and are poorly-understood. In addition, nanoparticles can stick together in a process known as 'agglomeration' or 'clumping', which could reduce their effectiveness in trapping heat near the surface of Mars, and make them fall out of the atmosphere faster. As a result, we need to validate both the wind lofting of the aerosols and their tendency to agglomerate. This can be achieved either with the warming particles themselves or with nanoparticles whose aerodynamic and clumping properties can be correlated with those of the warming agent.

The main goal of the mission is to track a small mass (<1 kg) of aerosol up to 200 m in altitude and 1 km in range to demonstrate its dispersal into the atmosphere, while quantifying the particle size distribution at release.

Fig. 4 Precursor mission payload release test on the Martian surface (artist's impression by Vlad Socianu)

While full scale Mars warming elements such as the development of In-Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU) technology can be heavily de-risked on Earth, plume dispersal cannot be de-risked without a Mars surface release test. This is because:

- While we can recreate reduced atmospheric pressure conditions with the ARC Planetary Aeolian Laboratory at NASA Ames that can be pumped down to 5 mbar for an operating volume of 141.000 ft³, we cannot couple it with reduced Mars gravity which plays an important role in the near-surface turbulence.
- In addition, even the largest Mars chamber in the world at NASA Ames (30 m high by 7 m in diameter) is not large enough to fully reproduce turbulent flow on Mars.
- Data on the wind velocity and direction on Mars is sparse: models use the few data points gathered by probes on the surface or by tracking dust devils from orbit [9]. A good example of the lack of reliability of wind data is that the *Ingenuity Mars* helicopter encountered winds twice as fast as expected on its flights [10].

Design, development and testing work on Earth will rely on Large Eddy Simulations (LES) [11] that provide the best modeling of our aerosol dispersal test (Fig. 5), but in the end only a real surface experiment on Mars can help us understand the particle dispersal mechanisms as well as the effectiveness of any anti-clumping methods implemented.

Fig. 5 Large Eddy Simulation of particle dispersal. The plume is shown in the top right corner of the simulation domain. The X axis units are meters and the atmosphere height is 10 m.

Synergies With Human Needs on Mars

While a surface release test is needed to validate the atmospheric transport of the engineered aerosols, this science investigation is well aligned with overall planetary science exploration goals and can help with understanding the causes of hazardous dust storms that threaten human and robotic missions to Mars. The Planetary Science Decadal Survey [12] and the Mars Exploration Program Analysis Group (MEPAG) [13] both call for low-cost surface payloads that quantify transport mechanisms within the near-surface atmosphere. In addition, the National Academies of Sciences Consensus Study Report on the Science Strategy For The Human Exploration of Mars [14] prioritizes research on the “onset and evolution of major dust storms” and “the effects of Martian dust on human physiology and hardware lifetime”.

Thus, the precursor mission to Mars is aimed at tackling four key areas of scientific uncertainty for future Mars exploration:

- Atmosphere & modern climate: through performing the first aerosol tracking experiment in Mars' atmosphere to understand planetary boundary layer (PBL) fluxes.
- Human exploration: through investigations of the dust cycle since dust is a key hazard to humans and spacecraft [15].
- Planetary protection: through the release of aerosols that are of similar dimensions to microbes, to assess the downwind travel of microbes released by human activities.
- Mars terraforming: through the release and tracking of aerosols relevant to Mars warming.

But how are we actually going to achieve all of this?

$$N_S(R) = N_0 k_T k_R G(R) \left(\frac{A}{R^2} \right) \left(\frac{c\tau}{2} \right) \beta(R) \exp \left[-2 \int_0^R \sigma(r) dr \right]$$

where [16]:

- $N_S(R)$ is the number of laser photons received in a bin at range R per laser pulse,
- N_0 is the number of photons in each laser pulse,
- k_T is the optical efficiency of the transmitter,
- k_R is the optical efficiency of the receiver,
- $G(R)$ is the geometrical function,
- $\left(\frac{A}{R^2} \right)$ is the receiver solid angle (sr),
- $c\tau / 2$ is the range bin length (m)
- $\beta(R)$ is the volume backscatter coefficient ($\text{m}^{-1}\text{sr}^{-1}$), and
- $\sigma(r)$ is the extinction coefficient (m^{-1}).

The heritage for aerosol tracking experiments from the Martian surface is the lidar that flew on the Phoenix lander in 2008 [17]. This lidar showed that clouds on Mars can be tracked

with a small (6 kg) surface based laser and it demonstrates the feasibility of our science measurement concept. The Phoenix lidar operated at two wavelengths in the visible range (532 nm) and the IR range (1064 nm) and tracked clouds higher than 10 km.

Fig. 6 The Phoenix lidar with the cover removed (left) and a schematic of the laser transmitter (right) [17]

While the tracking range is shorter for our mission (1 km vs 10 km), the aerosol particle concentration is on the order of $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at 1 km, while the clouds detected by the Phoenix lidar at 10 km had an ice water content 1-2 orders of magnitude higher. As a result, a higher performance lidar may be necessary. In the context of the decreasing cost of access to the Martian surface and with present day lidar technology, it is safe to assume that a more capable lidar can be developed for our mission. Mars Lidars under development include MARBL (30mJ, 10 Hz) [18], MARLI (4 mJ, 1 kHz) [19] and the Mars lander lidar (0.1 mJ, 10 kHz) [20].

A secondary remote sensing instrument that will be used is a set of wide field of view engineering cameras that can detect the initial release of the plume.

Together with the lidar, a sonic anemometer is needed because the particle release events have to be synchronized with wind updrafts. This requires an instrument with a high measurement frequency (up to 10-20 Hz) and accuracy (± 0.1 m/s). Anemometers currently on Mars operate at a frequency of around 1 Hz and accuracy of 0.5 - 1 m/s, while the Martian acoustic anemometer currently in development at NASA Ames [21] can meet these requirements.

Finally, to quantify particle size distribution and particle concentration near the release point, a nephelometer is being considered. The nephelometer will complement the long range lidar measurements with in-situ clumping data. Nephelometers measure the laser light backscattered from particles in the atmosphere and they use the reflected signal to measure particle density, size and shape [22]. Nephelometers have flown before to Venus (1978) and Jupiter (1995). Another is planned to be used on the upcoming Rocket Lab mission to Venus.

Fig. 7 An example of potential payload instruments: lidar (left) [17], anemometer (center) [21], engineering camera (top right) [23] and nephelometer (bottom right) [24]

Aerosol Dispersal

These instruments for tracking the plume are under development within certain research groups or have flown to space in some configuration in the past, but the particle storage and release mechanism is a different story. While NASA has done plume release experiments in space before (including CRRES and the Charged Aerosol Release Experiments), no particle release experiment has taken place on a different planet and especially in the challenging conditions on Mars. On Earth, particle dispensers are used for filter calibration, crop-spraying, aerosolized drug delivery, and powder-based manufacturing. These applications may require either large aerosol flowrates, a well controlled particle size distribution, or the ability to avoid clumping on the nano scale, but these requirements are rarely met at the same time. We are well outside traditional industrial envelopes for our release and tracking application that requires:

- An aerosol flow rate >1 g/s range to maintain a high enough particle concentration for lidar detection at hundreds of meters range.
- Compatibility with sub-micron particles, since the aerodynamic diameter of the warming aerosol is ~ 300 nm.
- A monodisperse (non-clumped) flow to maximize residence time in the upper atmosphere and meet science requirements

These competing requirements suggest a multi-stage custom-designed particle dispenser that works as follows:

- Particle storage: the particles will be shipped from Earth in a closed container. The storage vessel will mitigate humidity and shake the particles intermittently to reduce the clumping behavior.
- Particle transport: to feed the particles from the storage container to the dispersal system, a mechanism such as a screw auger, piston, conveyer belt, or pneumatic entrainment will be used.
- Particle deagglomeration: the particles that come out of the particle storage system will be clumped and need to be broken down for release. Nanoparticle clumps can be deagglomerated with high shear flows, surface impaction, or mechanical grinding.
- Particle charging and release: following deagglomeration, the nanoparticle monomers will be pneumatically transported to the exit nozzle for release. As the particles exit the system, a coronal discharge will apply a negative charge to each particle to prevent short term coagulation. This is routinely done for Earth aerosols both in the laboratory and for industrial-scale aerosol manufacturing [25].

Fig. 8 Block diagram of the particle dispenser system

The design of the particle dispenser depends on the properties (density, aspect ratio, size) of the particles it has to process and release. The particles that would fly as part of the precursor mission must:

- Have a similar aerodynamic diameter to the warming particles (300-400 nm for 9 micron long metal rods).

- Have good backscatter properties to ensure a high signal to noise ratio (SNR) from the lidar ($Q_{\text{back}} > 5$).
- Have a low aspect ratio to prevent tangling at release. Based on [26], high aspect ratio particles like our warming agent clump up to 20 faster than spherical particles.
- Be available off-the-shelf to allow for testing today.

Fig. 9 Elements of the lab set-up used to investigate particle dispersal: (a) Palas particle dispenser [27] and scanning mobility particle sizer; (b) small scale prototype lidar; (c) prototype air classifier; (d) observation of fluorescent particles dispersed on sand

These requirements rule out flying the actual warming agents because by design they have poor backscatter properties in the visible ($Q_{\text{back}} < 1$), they have high aspect ratio (50-150 for Al rods) and are currently only be produced at lab scale ($< \mu\text{g}$) which does not allow for release tests any time soon. By contrast, silica spheres with a median particle diameter around 350 nm and coated with TiO_2 which can provide a backscatter coefficient of 5-10 at a wavelength of 532 nm, can satisfy all these criteria. These are available off the shelf [6] and have already been used for lab testing at Astera.

Now that we understand some of the challenges of both tracking and dispersing nanoparticles on Mars, we can discuss the sizing of our surface payload and its expected activities on Mars.

Payload Sizing and Operations

To size the payload, we need to know the aerosol mass that has to be released at Mars for repeatable tracking of the particles. This requires an end to end calculation that relates the particle characteristics, the released mass and mass flow rate, clumping effects, plume dispersal modeling, and lidar photon backscatter to understand how the release conditions affect the signal to noise ratio at a given tracking range. The calculation workflow is shown in the diagram below.

Fig. 10 End to end calculation logic: from release conditions to lidar SNR.

For those interested, the **Technical Corner** at the end of this article details the plume dispersal and clumping models used to understand the plume evolution from the release

nozzle up to 1 km in range. The results include the expected aerosol concentration in the Mars atmosphere as a function of tracking range, and also within the plume itself. This matters because it is important not only to understand what aerosol mass is required per release for a certain SNR, but also how accurately the lidar needs to point to ensure that SNR value.

Based on our current model and with the assumptions listed in the Technical Corner, we need to release 200 g of aerosol at 10 g/s and apply 5 negative charges per particle to ensure a signal to noise ratio of above 100 at 1 km. This is equivalent to having at least 1 μg of aerosol per m^3 at 1 km, or 20 particles per cm^3 (by comparison there are around 1-3 dust particles per cm^3 on average in the Martian atmosphere outside of dust season [28]).

These numbers will change as we improve our models and include LES outputs. However, they provide an entry point for understanding of the problem. If we assume that we want enough aerosol for 10 dispersals, we need to carry around 2.5 kg of TiO_2 coated silica spheres to Mars. This is the starting point for the payload sizing which is detailed in the table below.

Element	Mass (kg)	Assumptions
Nanoparticles	2.5	SNR > 100 at 1 km and 200 g/release
Compressed gas	25	Required to entrain the aerosol. 10:1 ratio as a worst case.
Gas tank	35	Composite Overwrapped Pressure Vessel (COPV) tank at 300 bars
Dispersal system	25	Includes the charging step. Large uncertainty since it is under development.
Nanoparticle storage system	15	Tank plus any piezoelectric actuators that may be needed to shake the powder on the way to Mars

Instruments	28	Higher confidence given that they are under development at TRL 4-5. Lidar 20 kg (a more powerful version of MILI, MARBLI or the Phoenix Lidar), nephelometer 5 kg [24], sonic anemometer 1 kg [21], engineering cameras 2 kg [23].
Support systems	40 - 60	The mass of the power, structure, communications and thermal control systems depends a lot on whether our payload would ride on a rover or operate next to the lander.
System Margin (20%)	34 - 38	A system margin characteristic for Phase 0/A applied. The mass margin depends on the support systems.
TOTAL	~200 - 225	N/A

The overall payload mass budget is around 200-225 kg including a 20% system margin. The payload volume is $0.5-1 \text{ m}^3$. Both the mass and the volume of the payload are within the capabilities of rovers designed for Moon and Mars operations [29]. The mass, volume and power constraints will be defined at a later date by the launch vehicle and mobility provider. If the payload mass has to be reduced this can be done by accepting the science risk of fewer releases and by reducing the tracking range (for 1 kg of nanoparticles instead of 2.5 kg we can save more than 50 kg at system level).

Finally, a concept of operations is proposed for 30 sols of scientific operations and a total of 150 sols of survival on the surface, should a global dust storm occur during the mission. After landing on Mars, instrument commissioning will follow for the first 2-3 sols. After the instruments are calibrated, the anemometer will collect wind information for at least 16 hours per sol. A few sols into the surface mission, the payload will move to autonomous operations where the wind sensor will act as the semi-automatic trigger for particle release. The release will likely happen in the afternoon when convection and updrafts are expected to be strongest. As the first release is triggered, the lidar will track the plume for 2-3 minutes before it goes beyond the 1 km tracking range. At the same time, the engineering cameras will perform short range tracking (tens of meters) to confirm the plume release,

while the nephelometer will measure particle size distribution for the duration of the release (seconds to tens of seconds).

After the first release, the tracking data from all instruments as well as sensor data from inside the dispersal system will be processed on Earth. The tracking and dispersal settings may be adjusted for the next dispersal and the process will be repeated at least 5 times.

Fig. 11 Surface Concept of Operations (CONOPS) diagram

Conclusions

Research into making Mars more habitable is more active than ever and concepts that previously leaned towards science fiction, such as warming Mars to enable a wider variety of human activities on the surface, are now closer to science fact. The question of warming Mars with engineered aerosols involves many technical challenges, from the design of the aerosols, to their mass production, to their release and global dispersal, to their lifetime in

the atmosphere and long term biocompatibility. We are tackling all of these topics through our research, and sending a surface payload to Mars to perform the first nanoparticle release test on another planet can be a stepping stone in the future of humans on Mars. You can find more at marsterraforming.org.

Article by [Adrian Dumitrescu](#)

Thanks to Edwin Kite and Ashwin Braude for providing valuable feedback. And thank you to Alex Kling, Ari Essunfeld and Lily Coffin for all their inputs related to the work.

The set of inputs used for the current sizing of the plume release mass is shown below

Parameter	Value	Comments
Particle diameter	380 nm	SNR > 100 at 1 km and 200 g/release
Particle density	2000 kg/m ³	Required to entrain the aerosol. 10:1 ratio as a worst case.
Particle refractive index	2.6678 + 0j	TiO ₂ coating
Jet Velocity	75 m/s	To ensure a momentum ratio of 15 while assuming the same density for the plume and the wind
Horizontal wind speed	5 m/s	Characteristic for Mars [34]
Vertical wind speed	1 m/s	Characteristic for Mars [34]
Particle mass	200 g	Mass required for SNR in excess of 100
Particle mass flow rate	10 g/s	Flow rate for a short dispersal
Charge applied	-5e per particle	Intermediate charge level considered (-10e feasible)
Far-field plume growth model	Pasquill type B	Moderately unstable case as an initial assumption.
Lidar characteristics	All from [17] Exception: pulse energy 4 mJ instead of 0.4 mJ	Phoenix lidar with 10x the pulse energy
Lidar integration time	10 s	Reasonable for our application. May integrate for a shorter time and distance at close range for early pointing.
Lidar integration distance	10 m	
Lidar pointing error	0.5 sigma Y (60 m) 0.5 sigma Z (75 m)	Initial assumption. Better accuracy may be achieved.
Atmosphere spectral radiance	10.2 [W*m ⁻² *microns ⁻¹ *sr ⁻¹]	Worst case detected by Phoenix Lidar

- [1] 2024 Mars Terraforming Workshop Proceedings, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11390070>
- [2] DeBenedictis, E.A., et al., 2025. The case for Mars terraforming research. *Nature Astronomy*, 9(5), pp.634-639.
- [3] Ansari, S. et al., 2024. *Feasibility of keeping Mars warm with nanoparticles*. *Science Advances*, Vol 10, No 32. DOI:10.1126/sciadv.adn4650
- [4] Richardson, M.I. et al., 2025. Atmospheric dynamics of first steps toward terraforming Mars. arXiv preprint arXiv:2504.01455.
- [5] Fang, Z. et al., 2013. Gated tunability and hybridization of localized plasmons in nanostructured graphene. *ACS Nano*, 7(3), pp.2388-2395.
- [6] Cospheric Monodisperse Silica Microspheres. URL: https://www.cospheric.com/SiO2MS_monodisperse_silica_spheres_beads_nm_microns.htm
- [7] MSE Supplies, MSE PRO High Purity Alpha Aluminium Oxide Nanoparticles
- [8] Kite, E., 2025. Fostering a world-scale biosphere on Mars: a research agenda. Substack, URL: <https://marsterraforming.substack.com/p/research-towards-fostering-a-world>
- [9] Bickel, V.T., et al., 2025. Dust devil migration patterns reveal strong near-surface winds across Mars. *Science advances*, 11(41), p.eadw5170.
- [10] Jackson, B., et al., 2024. Profiling Near-Surface Winds on Mars Using Attitude Data from Mars 2020 Ingenuity. arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.19132.
- [11] Wu, Z., et al., 2021. Large eddy simulations of the dusty Martian convective boundary layer with MarsWRF. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 126(9), p.e2020JE006752.
- [12] National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. 2023. *Origins, Worlds, and Life: Planetary Science and Astrobiology in the Next Decade*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press.
- [13] Mars Exploration Program Analysis Group (MEPAG), 2025. *Mars Science Goals, Objectives, Investigations, and Priorities: 2025 Version*.

- [14] National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. 2025. A Science Strategy for the Human Exploration of Mars. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press.
- [15] Beaty, D.W., et al., 2005. An Analysis of the Precursor Measurements of Mars Needed to Reduce the Risk of the First Human Mission to Mars. Unpublished white paper, 77 p, posted June, 2005 by the Mars Exploration Program Analysis Group (MEPAG) at <http://mepag.jpl.nasa.gov/reports/index.html>.
- [16] Gimmestad, G. G., Roberts, D.W., 2023. Lidar Engineering: Introduction to Basic Principles. Cambridge University Press, ISBN 978-0-521-19851-6 Hardback. DOI: 10.1017/9781139014106
- [17] Whiteway, J., et al., 2008. Lidar on the Phoenix mission to Mars. JOURNAL OF GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH, VOL. 113, E00A08, doi:10.1029/2007JE003002
- [18] Määttänen, A., et al., 2017. The marbl experiment: towards a martian wind lidar. EPJ Web of Conferences, 2018, The 28th International Laser Radar Conference (ILRC 28), Bucharest 2017, 176, art. 06006 (4 p.). [ff10.1051/epjconf/201817606006ff](https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/201817606006).
- [19] Cremons, D.R., et al., 2020. Design of a direct-detection wind and aerosol lidar for mars orbit. CEAS Space Journal, 12(2), pp.149-162.
- [20] Abshire, J.B., et al., 2025. Design of a small lidar for a Mars lander to profile water vapor, aerosols, and winds. In Laser Radar Technology and Applications XXX (Vol. 13472, pp. 61-75). SPIE.
- [21] Cheng, T.J., et al., 2024. Test Flight of a Stratospheric Sonic Anemometer Prototype. Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology, 41(12), pp.1139-1149.
- [22] Jha, V., et al., 2020. A laser nephelometer for direction of in-situ particles in planetary atmosphere. 51st Lunar and Planetary Science Conference.
- [23] Maki, J., et al., 2024. INGENUITY MARS HELICOPTER CAMERAS: DESCRIPTION AND RESULTS. 10th International Conference on Mars.
- [24] Soto, A., et al., 2020. HURA: An instrument for atmospheric and aeolian science. Sixth International Planetary Dunes Workshop.

- [25] Hinds, W.C. and Zhu, Y., 2022. *Aerosol technology: properties, behavior, and measurement of airborne particles*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [26] Boies, A.M., et al., 2019. Agglomeration Dynamics of 1D Materials: Gas-Phase Collision Rates of Nanotubes and Nanorods. *Small*, 15(27), p.1900520.
- [27] RGB 1000 System, PALAS. URL: <https://www.palas.de/en/product/rbg1000?save=accept>
- [28] Fedorova, A.A., et al., 2009. Solar infrared occultation observations by SPICAM experiment on Mars-Express: Simultaneous measurements of the vertical distributions of H₂O, CO₂ and aerosol. *Icarus*, 200(1), pp.96-117.
- [29] Astrolab Venturi, FLEX Payload Interface Guide, 2022.
- [30] Smith, S.H. and Mungal, M.G., 1998. Mixing, structure and scaling of the jet in crossflow. *Journal of fluid mechanics*, 357, pp.83-122.
- [31] Seinfeld, J.H. and Pandis, S.N., 2016. *Atmospheric chemistry and physics: from air pollution to climate change*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [32] Hanna, S.R., Briggs, G.A. and Hosker Jr, R.P., 1981. *Handbook on atmospheric diffusion* (No. DOE/TIC-11223). National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Oak Ridge, TN (USA). Atmospheric Turbulence and Diffusion Lab.
- [33] Fric, T.F. and Roshko, A., 1994. Vortical structure in the wake of a transverse jet. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 279, pp.1-47.
- [34] Banfield, D., et al., 2020. The atmosphere of Mars as observed by InSight. *Nature Geoscience*, 13(3), pp.190-198.